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New and confirmed records of *Heterarthrus flavicollis* (Gussakovskij, 1947) from Hungary with an annotated checklist of Hungarian *Heterarthrus species* (Hymenoptera, Tenthredinidae)

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Abstract. This paper presents the first documented occurrence of *Heterarthrus flavicollis* (Gussakovskij, 1947) in Hungary. The author discovered its leaf-mines on *Acer platanoides* and confirmed its presence in the region, extending the known southern boundary of the species' distribution to the 44th parallel (Serbia). The study outlines the species' biology, noting its univoltine lifecycle and distinctive pupal cocoon formation. Additionally, the paper provides an annotated checklist of *Heterarthrus* species found in Hungary, detailing their biology and distribution. The research contributes to the broader understanding of leaf-mining sawflies in Central Europe.

Keywords. first record, habitat, Hungarian, *Heterarthrus* species

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Introduction

In recent years, the author has researched the life history and geographical distribution of leaf-mining insects (Fazekas 2011, 2024), with particular emphasis on leaf-mining moths. These investigations consistently examined grassland plants, shrubs, and tree species. During the research, the author encountered a leaf-mine on the leaves of *Acer platanoides* that was previously unknown to him. Upon identification, it was ascertained to be a leaf miner of *Heterarthrus flavicollis* (Gussakovskij, 1947). Notably, this species had not been documented in Hungary before this discovery. In this study, a summary of the records of this species is presented, and an annotated list of *Heterarthrus* species in Hungary is provided, detailing their geographical distribution and significant bionomic data.

***Heterarthrus flavicollis* (Gussakovskij, 1947)**

Phyllotoma flavicollis Gussakovskij, 1947. Type locality: Georgia, Tbilisi.

Observations in Europe (Literature and internet*, ** data):

Georgia, Tbilisi (Gussakovskij, 1947), Tbilisi 400–1000 m asl., 15. 05. 1980, Tbilisi 470–850 m asl., Gori 480 m asl., Abastumani, 1300 m asl. (Supatashvili et al. 2022)

Armenia, Kirovakan, Bot. Garden, 15.vi.1966. (Zombori, 2022)

Russia, Moscow, (Zsukovka, 6.vi.2021, 1 larva in mines on *Acer platanoides*), Zolotilovo*

Sweden, Skåne, Eslor, Kullaberg

Estonia, Karilats *

Lithuania, Mirkliai*, Panevėžys ? Vilnius*

Germany, Bad Gandersheim,
Slovakia, Bratislava, Patrónka, 17. vi. 2019, 4 larvae in mines on *Acer platanoides*
(Macek et al. 2020),
Serbia: Košutnjak (Dobrosavljević and Marković, 2017)

More confirmed data in Hungary:

Hungary, Budapest (Hüvösvölgy, neighbourhood), 3. vii. 2019, 1 larva in mines on *Acer platanoides*), (Ellis 2025).

Pécs (Tettye, 7-12.v. 2025, | 46.08701N, 18.123747E | 12 larvae in mines on *Acer platanoides*, © Fazekas Imre)

Pécs (Péter utca, 15.v. 2025, | 46.08227N, 18.22647E | 6 larvae in mines on *Acer platanoides*, © Fazekas Imre)

Pécs (Péter utca, 15.v. 2025, | 46.08227N, 18.22647E | 6 larvae in mines on *Acer platanoides*, © Fazekas Imre)

Pécs (Puskin tér, 21.v.2025, | 46.08487N, 18.26267E | 2 larvae in mines on *Acer platanoides*, © Fazekas Imre)

Kaposvár, Fő utca 03.05.2025. | 46.35702N, 17.79986E | 1 larva in mines on *Acer platanoides*, © Fazekas Imre)

Fig. 1. First valid observation site in Hungary of *Heterarthrus falvicollis*: Pécs, Tettye, 7–12.v. 2025, | 12 larvae in mines on *Acer platanoides*, © Fazekas Imre, The white arrow shows the *Acer platanoides* tree at 350 m a.s.l.

Fig. 2. Morphology of the *Heterarthrus flavicollis* leaf mines. The cocoon falls off the leaf before the leaf falls off the tree. (white arrow).

Host plants and biology. *Acer platanoides* L. (Altenhofer and Zombori 1987). The mine starts near the middle of the leaf (Liston 1995). The cocoon falls off the leaf before the leaf falls off the tree. Univoltine.

According to Voolma (2019), the mines appear as irregular brown spots on the leaf. When the larva has finished feeding and growing, it must pupate. To do this, it makes a disc-shaped, lentil-shaped cocoon inside the leaf at the edge of the cavity and cuts through the leaf's covering layer in a regular circle around it so that the disc-shaped cocoon falls out of the leaf. The author found the disc-shaped cocoons in the dry grass under the tree.

Dobrosavljević and Marković (2017) report that in Serbia, *H. flavicollis* is a monophagous species whose larvae create mines in the central region of *Acer platanoides* L. leaves. Initially, the larvae consume only the mesophyll beneath the upper epidermis, eventually consuming

Fig. 3. Preliminary geographical distribution map of *Heterarthrus flavicollis* on the basis of literature and new observations in Hungary.

nearly all of it, resulting in the formation of transparent mines of irregular shapes on the leaf. Solitary larvae, characterised by reduced legs and distinctive sclerotised surfaces on their dorsal and abdominal sides, develop within these mines. As they near the end of their development, the larvae construct a discoidal cocoon inside the mine, which subsequently detaches along with a disc cut from the upper epidermal layer that remains attached to the cocoon.

Distribution. Central Europe, Serbia, north to southern Sweden (Taeger et al. 2006), but it is rarely recorded, and its occurrence is very local. Based on recent observations in Hungary, the southern limit of the species' range in Europe is at the 44th parallel.

Annotated list of *Heterarthrus* species of Hungary

Note: In the annotation, I have considered the literature listed in the references.

Heterarthrus Stephens, 1835

The genus *Heterarthrus* encompasses 22 species predominantly distributed across the Palaearctic region. One species lives in the Oriental region, and two species have been introduced to North America: *Heterarthrus nemoratus* (Fallén, 1808) and *H. vagans* (Fallén, 1808).

In Hungary, this genus is represented by eight species: *Heterarthrus aceris*, *H. cuneifrons*, *H. leucomela*, *H. wuestneii*, *H. microcephalus*, *H. ochropoda*, and *H. vagans*, in addition to *Heterarthrus flavicollis*. As Zombori (1982) noted, these species are characterised by their small and elongated form, with lengths ranging from 3 to 7 mm. The larvae, which are leaf miners, develop within the foliage of various deciduous trees, including those belonging to the families Aceraceae, Betulaceae, and Salicaceae. Their morphology is highly specialised for this ecological niche, featuring small, flattened heads and atrophied thoracic legs. The initia-

tion of their mines typically occurs at the leaf tip or along one side of the tip. On smaller or younger leaves, they often consume the entire leaf content. The mature larvae construct a circular, light brown, transparent pupal chamber, approximately 10 mm in diameter, within the petiole, and they overwinter in the leaf litter following leaf abscission.

Altenhofer (1980) described in detail the anatomy of *Heterarthrus* cocoons and distinguished between two different behavioural groups: those species in which the cocoon detaches from the leaf before leaf drop and those in which the cocoon remains in the leaf until after leaf drop. It is believed that only *Acer*-feeding species (except *H. leucomela*) use the former strategy.

The cocoons of 'detached' species can be moved by the rapid movement of their inhabitants, so that the cocoon eventually reaches the top layer of soil, where there is presumably less risk of drying out than in a leaf still on the tree. It is noteworthy that the larvae of *H. leucomela*, a species that feeds on *Acer*, develop much longer than any other species, so they should not survive the hottest and driest part of the year in their cocoon, remaining in the leaf. However, differences in behaviour may also result from other types of selection pressure, such as predation.

***Heterarthrus flora* Liston, 2019**

= *Heterarthrus aceris* auct. nec Kaltenbach, 1856

Localities in Hungary: Budapest (Hűvösvölgy and Svábhegy) (Zombori, 1982a), Nagyhatos, Pécs, Ócsa (Roller and Haris, 2008), Budapest (Mártonhegy, Hűvösvölgy), Nagykovácsi, Dunaujváros, Fertő–Hanság NP, Kapuvár (Madárvárta), Aggteleki Nemzeti Park, Jósvalő (Lófej-völgy), Rahó, Alsóláz (Zombori, 2022).

The larvae mine in the leaves of *Acer pseudoplatanus* in June–July. The leaf mine starts at the tip of a leaf lobe. An exclusively parthenogenetic species, whose male is unknown.

Distribution: Widespread in Europe, including the British Isles; south to Sicily and reaching southern Sweden in the North-Armenia.

***Heterarthrus cuneifrons* (Altenhofer and Zombori, 1987)**

Localities in Hungary: Miskolc (Zombori, 1996a)

Among the four *Heterarthrus* species that feed on *Acer* species are *H. flora* (previously misidentified as *H. aceris*), *H. cuneifrons*, *H. wuestneii*. Historically, these species have been subject to taxonomic confusion. The larvae of *H. cuneifrons* mine the leaves of sycamore maple from within the leaf blade, whereas *Heterarthrus flora* initiates its mine at the leaf margin. *Heterarthrus leucomela* also mines *Acer pseudoplatanus* (but also *A. campestre*). While the cocoons of *H. leucomela* remain in the leaf until the leaf falls from the tree, the cocoons of the other maple-feeding *Heterarthrus* fall out of the leaf shortly after the cocoon has been made. Two larvae can sometimes be observed in one mine, but only one larva is usually present. A circular puparium is formed from the upper epidermis of the leaf, which detaches from the leaf before autumn leaf fall, leaving a discernible hole in the leaf. The puparium subsequently enters the litter layer. (See: <https://www.sawflies.org.uk/heterarthrus-cuneifrons/>)

Distribution: The species has been observed in Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, the Netherlands, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom (specifically in England and Wales). Approximately 200 sightings have been documented, predominantly in Western Europe, such as the Benelux region. It is a highly localised species, with occurrences primarily in central, southern, and eastern Europe.

***Heterarthrus leucomela* (Klug, 1814)**

Localities in Hungary: Nagyvisnyó (Zombori, 1976a), Nagykovácsi (Zombori, 2022), Bükk Mts. (Csipkésút) (Zombori, 2022), Miskolc (Szentlélek) (Roller and Haris, 2008).

Its larvae develop in the leaves of *Acer campestre* and *A. pseudoplatanus*.

Distribution: It is widespread in continental Europe, including Austria, the Czech Republic, Germany, Hungary, mainland Italy, Poland, Slovakia, and Ukraine.

***Heterarthrus wuestneii* (Konow, 1905)**

= *Heterarthrus healyi* Altenhofer et Zombori, 1987

Localities in Hungary (present and historical): Widespread (Szöcs et al. 2015); Nagykovácsi, Barnabás, Odvas (Zombori, 2022) and Mosonmagyaróvár (Ellis 2025).

Its larvae develop in the leaves of *Acer campestre* L. and *A. monspessulanum* L.

Widely distributed in Europe from the Mediterranean north to Denmark and the British Isles (Taeger et al. 2006, Liston et al. 2019).

***Heterarthrus microcephalus* (Klug, 1818),**

Localities in Hungary: Fenyőfő (Zombori, 1979a), Csepel, Gyón, Máriabesnyő, Nagykovácsi, Mecsek Mts., Bakony Mts. (Zombori, 1982a), Csévharaszt (Zombori, 1985c, 2022), Győr (Roller and Haris, 2008), Nagylóc: Alsó-Zsúny (Haris, 2021).

Larvae develop within the leaves of various willow species, including *Salix caprea*, *S. alba*, *S. viminalis*, and *S. daphnoides*. The pit extends inward from the leaf tip and may occupy up to half or the entirety of the leaf, contingent upon its size. The larvae may undergo 2–3 generations annually. They are collected from May to September.

Distribution: Widely distributed in Europe (Taeger et al. 2006), to the north of the Arctic circle, the British Isles, and the Iberian Peninsula; Transpalearctic through Armenia, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, West and East Siberia to the Russian Far East (Sundukov 2017). Its occurrence in Iran is questionable.

***Heterarthrus ochropoda* (Klug, 1818),**

Localities in Hungary: Szigetszentmiklós (Zombori, 1975a), Kapuvár (Zombori, 2002), Bátorligeti-láp (Zombori, 1990b), Zamárdi (Tőreki-láp), Nagykovácsi (Zombori, 2022), Famos, Kecskemét (Roller and Haris, 2008).

The larvae excavate irregular burrows in the leaves of *Populus alba*, *P. nigra*, and *P. tremula*. They create vesicular mines on poplar trees, with a particular affinity for the European Aspen (*P. tremula*). The larvae expel the litter from the mine to clear it.

Distribution: The distribution extends throughout much of Europe, including the British mainland, but it has not been documented in the Iberian Peninsula (Taeger et al. 2006). Additionally, it is found in Turkey, Kyrgyzstan, West and East Siberia, and the Russian Far East (Sundukov 2017).

***Heterarthrus vagans* (Fallén, 1808),**

Localities in Hungary: Csorna (Zombori, 2002), Kaposmérő (Haris, 1998b), Nagyhatos, Pécs, Ócsa, Szilvásvár (Zombori, 1996a) Magyaregres (Haris, 2018). Berzence: Alsó-Gyóta erdő (Alsó-Gyóta forest), Filagoria (Haris, 2012); Nagylóc: Alsó-Zsúny (Haris, 2021).

Its larvae develop in a blistered mine in the leaves of *Alnus glutinosa*, and *Betula* spp. often in a single mine with several individuals. They form a circular puparium in the shaft, which remains in the leaf. Up to 2 generations may develop in a year.

Distribution: *H. vagans* is prevalent across Europe, encompassing the British Isles and the Iberian Peninsula (Taeger et al. 2006), extending from north of the Arctic Circle to several major Mediterranean islands, and is also found in Turkey (Muche 1983). It has been introduced to western North America, specifically in British Columbia and Washington (Humble 2010, Looney et al. 2016). Sundukov (2017) notes that *H. vagans* exhibits a broad distribution throughout the East Palearctic, reaching the Russian Far East. Nevertheless, records from some of these regions may pertain to *H. kamtchaticus*, necessitating verification of voucher specimens.

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References

- Altenhofer E. 1980: Zur Biologie der in Baumblättern minierenden Blattwespen (Hym.,10) Zeitschrift für angewandte Entomologie 89: 122–134.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0418.1980.tb03451.x>
- Altenhofer E. & Zombori L. 1987: The species of *Heterarthrus* Stephens, 1835 feeding on maple (Hymenoptera, Tenthredinidae). – *Annales historico-naturales Musei Nationalis Hungarici* 79: 185–197.
- Antropov A.V., Astafurova Yu.V., Belokobylskij S.A., Byvaltsev A.M., Danilov Yu.N., Dubovikoff D.A., Fadeev K.I., Fateryga A.V., Kurzenko N.V., Lelej A.S., Levchenko T.V., Loktionov V.M., Mokrousov M.V., Nemkov P.G., Proshchalykin M.Yu., Rosa P., Sidorov D.A., Sundukov Yu.N., Yusupov Z.M. & Zaytseva L.A. 2017: Annotated catalogue of the Hymenoptera of Russia volume I Symphyta and Apocrita: Aculeata. – *Proceedings of the Zoological Institute RAS Supplement* 6, 475 p.
- Dobrosavljević J. & Marković Č. 2017: *Hinatara nigripes* (Konow) i *Heterarthrus flavicollis* (Gussakovskij) (Hymenoptera, Tenthredinidae), nove vrste lisnih minera u fauni Srbije. In *Proceedings of the XI Simpozijum Entomologa Srbije*; Glaven
- Ellis W.N. 2001–2025: Plant parasites of Europe: leaf miners, galls and fungi. – <https://bladmineerders.nl> (visited May 20, 2025)
- Fazekas I. 2011: Az *Agromyza flaviceps* Fallén, 1823 új előfordulása a Mecsekben | New occurrence of *Agromyza flaviceps* Fallén, 1823 in Mecsek Mountains (Diptera: Agromyzidae). – *e-Acta Naturalia Pannonica* 2(3): 193–198.
- Fazekas I. 2024: Distribution and Bionomy of *Stigmella aceris* (Frey, 1857) and *Stigmella speciosa* (Frey, 1858) in Hungary (Lepidoptera, Nepticulidae). – *Lepidopterologica Hungarica* 20(2): 35–43.
- Haris A. 1998: A Somogy Megyei Múzeum levéldarázs-gyűjteménye (Hymenoptera, Symphyta). – *Somogyi Múzeumok Közleményei* 13: 275–285.
- Haris A. 2012: Sawflies of Belső-Somogy (Hymenoptera: Symphyta). – *Natura Somogyiensis* 22: 141–162.
- Haris A. 2018: Sawflies from Külső-Somogy, South-West Hungary (Hymenoptera: Symphyta). – *Natura Somogyiensis* 32: 147–164.
- Haris A. 2021: Sawflies of the Cserhát Mountains (Hymenoptera: Symphyta). – *Natura Somogyiensis* 37: 25–42. doi:10.24394/NatSom.2021.37.25
- Humble L.M. 2010: First North American records for *Heterarthrus vagans* (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae), a Palearctic leaf mining sawfly of alder. – *The Canadian Entomologist* 142(2):181–187. doi:10.4039/n09-071
- Liston A.D. 1993a: *Heterarthrus flavicollis* (Gussakovskij) (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae): a new European leaf-miner on *Acer platanoides* L. – *Entomologist's Gazette* 44: 299–301.
- Liston A.D. 1993c. *Heterarthrus flavicollis* (Gussakovskij) (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae): a new European leaf-miner on *Acer platanoides* L. – *Entomologist's Gazette* 44: 299–301.
- Liston A.D. 1995a: Compendium of European Sawflies. List of species, modern nomenclature, distribution, foodplants, identification literature. – *Chalastos Forestry*, Gottfrieding, 190 p.
- Liston A.D. 1995b: *Heterarthrus flavicollis* (Gussakovskij, 1947) (Hym., Tenthredinidae): probable occurrence in Germany and description of the leaf-mine. – *The Entomologist's Monthly Magazine* 131: 126.
- Liston A., Mutanen M. & Viitasaari M. 2019: On the taxonomy of *Heterarthrus* (Hymenoptera, Tenthredinidae), with a review of the West Palearctic species. – *Journal of Hymenoptera Research* 72: 83–126.
 doi: [dx.doi.org/10.3897/jhr.72.39339](https://doi.org/10.3897/jhr.72.39339)
- Macek J., Roller, L., Beneš K., Holý K. & Holusa, J. 2020: Blanokřídlí České a Slovenské republiky II. Siropasí. – *Academia*, Praha, 669 p.
- Roller L. & Haris A. 2008: Sawflies of the Carpathian Basin, History and Current Research. – *Natura Somogyiensis* 11: 1–261.

- Sundukov Y.N. 2017: Suborder Symphyta – Sawflies and Wood Wasps. In: Belokobylskij S.A. & Lelej A.S. (Eds): Annotated Catalogue of the Hymenoptera of Russia (Volume 1). Symphyta and Apocrita: Aculeata. – Trudy Zoologicheskogo Instituta Rossijskoj Akademii Nauk, Supplement 6: 20–117.
- Supatashvili A., Japoshvili G. & Haris A. 2022: Some important records on sawflies (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) from the Entomological Collection of Agricultural University of Georgia (Sakartvelo) identified by Dr. Ermolenko. – *Natura Somogyiensis* 39: 47–58.
- Szöcs L., George M., Thuróczy Cs. & Csóka Gy. 2015: Contribution to the knowledge of the parasitoid fauna of leaf mining sawflies (Hymenoptera: Tenthredinidae) of forest plants in Hungary. – *Periodicum Biologorum* 117(4): 527–532.
- Taeger A. & Blank S.M. 2013: Fauna Europaea: Symphyta. Fauna Europaea version 2.6.2. – [http://www. faunaeur.org](http://www.faunaeur.org)
- Taeger A., Blank S. M. & Liston A. D. 2006: European Sawflies (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) - A Species Checklist for the Countries. 399–504. – In: Blank S. M., Schmidt S. & Taeger A. (Eds) Recent Sawfly Research: Synthesis and Prospects. – Goecke & Evers, Kelttern.
- Wahlgren E. 1944. Bladminerande Tenthredinidlarver. – *Opuscula Entomologica* 9: 138–149.
- Zombori L. 1975: New sawfly species in the Hungarian fauna (Hymenoptera, Symphyta), I. – *Annales historico-naturales Musei Nationalis Hungarici* 67: 231–236.
- Zombori L. 1979: A Bakonyi Természettudományi Múzeum levéldarázs-gyűjteménye (Hymenoptera: Symphyta) II. – *A Veszprém Megyei Múzeumok Közleményei* 14: 211–220.
- Zombori L. 1982: Tenthredinoidea - Levéldarázs-alkatúak II. – In: *Fauna Hungariae, Akadémiai Kiadó, Budapest*, 153, 11(3/A), 144 p.
- Zombori L. 1985: The Symphyta (Hymenoptera) Fauna of the Kiskunság National Park. 357–363. – In: Mahunka S. (ed.): *The fauna of the Kiskunság National Park. – Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest.*
- Zombori L. 1990: Sawflies from Bátorliget (Hymenoptera: Symphyta). 593–599. - In: Mahunka S. (ed.): *The Bátorliget nature reserve – after forty years. – Studia Naturalia, Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest.*
- Zombori L. 1996: Symphyta from the Bükk National Park (Hymenoptera). 435–452. – In: Mahunka S. (ed.): *The fauna of the Bükk national park, II. – Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest.*
- Zombori L. 2002: Sawflies from Fertő-Hanság National Park (Hymenoptera: Symphyta). – In Mahunka, S. (ed.): *The fauna of the Fertő-Hanság National Park. – Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest, pp. 545–552.*
- Zombori L. 2022: A növényevődarázs-kártételek gyűjteménye a Magyar Természettudományi Múzeumban. – *Annales Musei Historico-Naturalis Hungarici* 114: 187–213. <https://doi.org/10.53019/AnnlsMusHistNatHung.2022.114.187>

References of websites

- *<https://www.inaturalist.org/taxa/956111-Heterarthrus-flavicollis> (13 observations)
- **<https://bladmineerders.nl/parasites/animalia/arthropoda/insecta/hymenoptera/symphyta/tenthredinoidea/tenthredinidae/heterarthrinae/heterarthrus/heterarthrus-flavicollis/>
- <https://www.sawflies.org.uk/>
- https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/gallery?taxon_key=3258735 (Accessed, 14.05.2025)